

ISSN: 3060-4966

JIZPI XABARNOMASI

ILMIY-TEXNIK JURNAL

- 05.00.00 - Texnika fanlari
- 05.02.00 - Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik.
Mashinasozlikda materiallarga ishlov berish.
Metallurgiya. Aviasiya texnikasi
- 05.03.00 - Asbobsozlik, metrologiya va axborot-o'lchov
asboblari va tizimlari
- 05.04.00 - Radiotexnika va aloqa
- 05.05.00 - Energetika va elektrotexnika.
Qishloq xo'jaligi ishlab chiqarishini elektrlashtirish
texnologiyasi. Elektronika
- 05.06.00 - To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat materiallari
va buyumlari texnologiyasi
- 05.07.00 - Qishloq xo'jaligi ishlab chiqarishini
mexanizasiyalash texnologiyasi
- 05.08.00 - Transport
- 05.09.00 - Qurilish
- 05.10.00 - Inson faoliyati xavfsizligi

2025

No 2

Muassis:

Jizzax politexnika instituti

JizPI xabarnomasi**ILMIY-TEKNIK JURNAL****Vestnik DjizPI****НАУЧНО-ТЕХНИЧЕСКИЙ
ЖУРНАЛ****Bulletin of JizPI****SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL
JOURNAL***Bir yilda to'rt marta chop etiladi.*Jizzax viloyati Matbuot
va axborot boshqarmasi
tomonidan 2019 yil
14 martda 06-042 raqam bilan
ro'yxatga olingan.**Nashr uchun mas'ul:**

K. Karimova

Bosishga ruxsat

etildi: 25.06.2025.

Qog'oz bichimi: 60x84 ¹/₈.

Bosma tabog'i: 13,5.

Ofset bosma. Ofset qog'ozi.

Adadi: 100 dona.

Bahosi kelishilgan narxda.

Buyurtma №14

“**JIZPI TIPOGRAFIYASI**” MChJ
tomonidan tayyorlangan.“**JIZPI TIPOGRAFIYASI**” MChJ

bosmaxonasida chop etildi.

130100, Jizzax shahri,

Islom Karimov shoh ko'chasi, 4 - uy.

Telefon: (+99888) 140 00 74**BOSH MUHARRIR:****A.USMANKULOV**, texnika fanlari doktori, professor**BOSH MUHARRIR O'RINBOSARI:****J.ABDUNAZAROV**, texnika fanlari doktori, professor**MAS'UL MUHARRIR****K.KARIMOVA**, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori**TAHRIR HAY'ATI:****S.M.Turobjonov**, texnika fanlari doktori, *akademik* (TDTU)**S.S. Shaumarov**, texnika fanlari doktori, professor (TDTrU)**U.Yu.Yuldashev**, fizika-matematika fanlari doktori, professor (JizPI)**J.N.Abdunazarov**, texnika fanlari doktori, professor (JizPI)**I.S.Shukurov**, texnika fanlari doktori, professor (SamGASU)**Q.J.Jumaniyozov**, texnika fanlari doktori, professor (TEITI)**M.T.Xodjiyev**, texnika fanlari doktori, professor (GuIDU)**A.Z.Mamatov**, texnika fanlari doktori, professor (TTYeSI)**S.L. Eshkobilov**, PhD, professor (AQSH)**M.Mikusova**, PhD, professor (Slovakia)**V.A.Kondratev**, texnika fanlari doktori, professor (Belarus)**M.M. Ganiyev**, texnika fanlari doktori, professor (Rossiya)**F.A. Egamberdiyev**, texnika fanlari doktori, dotsent (JizPI)**I.Z.Abbazov**, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent (JizPI)**W. Pangwei**, PhD, professor (Xitoy)**K. Kim**, PhD, professor (Janubiy Koreya)**K. Széll**, - PhD, Dotsent (Vengriya)**A. Cansiz** – PhD, Professor (Turkiya)**M. Pogatsnik** – PhD, Dotsent (Vengriya)**Sh. Madjidov** – DSc, Dotsent (Xitoy)**V.I. Rimshin**, texnika fanlari doktori, professor (Rossiya)**A.B. Zabiyeva**, PhD, dotsent (Qozog'iston)**S.X.Baxriev**, texnika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Tojikiston)**I.V.Yakimenko**, texnika fanlari doktori, professor (Rossiya)**S.O. Eshbekova**, fizika-matematika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent**O.K.Adilov**, texnika fanlari nomzodi, professor (JizPI)**Sh.M. Musayev**, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent (JizPI)**A.O. Sultonov**, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent (JizPI)**S.V.Djiyanbayev**, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent (JizPI)**G'I.Mamayev**, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent (JizPI)**O.B.Berdiyev**, texnika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (JizPI)**B.I.Matniyazov**, texnika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (JizPI)**S.A. Sattarov**, fizika-matematika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (JizPI)**G'.G'.Egamnazarov**, texnika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (JizPI)**B.B.Doniyorov**, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent (JizPI)**M.A.Doniyorova**, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent (JizPI)**T.A.Berdiyev**, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent (JizPI)**O'.I.Jamolov**, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent (JizPI)**S.A.Usmanov**, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, professor (JizPI)**A.A.Taylaqov**, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent (JizPI)**B.A.Tursunov**, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent (JizPI)**M.Anorboyev**, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent (JizPI)**E.Abdullayev**, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent (JizPI)**TEKNIK MUHARRIRLAR:****M.Eshqulov** - assistent o'qituvchi, (UZ, ENG, RUS)**X.Xamdama** – filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent (UZ)**M.Ziyayeva** - pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent (RU)**F.Xiloliddinova** - v.b.dotsent (ENG)**Tahririyat manzili:****Jizzax shahri, Islom Karimov shoh ko'chasi, 4-uy****Faks: (0372) 226-45-47. Rasmiy sayt jurnal.jizpi.uz**

MUNDARIJA

AVTOMOBILLAR VA QISHLOQ XO'JALIK MASHINALARI

1	<i>Nishonov Azizbek Orziqul o'g'li, Yusupov Ulug'bek Akmal o'g'li.</i> O'zbekiston respublikasida aholi harakatchanligining hozirgi holati va muammolari.....	7
2	<i>Baratov Ilhomjon Iskandar o'g'li, Bakirov Lutfilla Yuldashaliyevich, Mamayev G'ulom Ibrohimovich, Nishonov Azizbek Orziqul o'g'li, Yusupov Ulug'bek Akmal o'g'li.</i> Analysis of reducing the impact of pedestrian traffic on traffic flow in the road network.....	18
3	<i>Razzaqov Tura Xolmurodovich, Karimova Kamola Fuломовна, Алимова Зебо Хамидуллаевна, Эргашева Дилсўз Истамовна.</i> Результаты определения физико-механических свойств семенного вороха трав.....	24
4	<i>Исраилов Фазил Исмаилович.</i> Принципы формирования транспортно-складского комплекса при развитии логистической системы.....	29
5	<i>Tagayev Xolmurod Sultonovich.</i> Diagnostics in the industrial service of motor vehicles.....	36
6	<i>Abdumannopov Abdullo Maxamadsoli o'g'li, Mamadaliev Ziyotali Qaxorali o'g'li.</i> Kombinatsiyalashgan mashinaning tuproq maydalagich diametrini ishlov berish chuqurligiga bog'liqligini aniqlash.....	41
7	<i>Valiev Muhammadali Komiljon o'g'li, Sobirov Bekzodbek Akhmadjonovich.</i> Program-based case detection and warning system.....	46
8	<i>Ismoilov Mirjalol Ro'ziboy o'g'li, Yuldasheva Muhayyo Alimboyevna, Qadirov Islom Rayimbergan o'g'li.</i> Yangi konstruksiyadagi rotatsion kultivator sxemasini ishlab chiqish.....	53
9	<i>Makhammadjon Qobulov.</i> The theoretical framework for logistics management in transportation and storage facilities.....	62
10	<i>Xalmuxamedov Aziz Suratovich, Amirquliv Farrux Bahodir o'g'li.</i> Toshkent shahri jamoat transporti marshruti murakkabligiga ta'sir qiluvchi omillar tahlili va optimallashtirish usullari" (KHAY–Bunyodkor chorrahasi misolida).....	70
11	<i>Oqbuta Karimovich Adilov, Makhammadaliev Zakirjon Turashbekovich, Abdulkarimov Shahzod O'ktam o'g'li.</i> Avtomobil transportining ekologiyaga ta'sir darajasini baholash.....	81
12	<i>Qosimov Baxtiyor Axmatjonovich.</i> Elektromobillar va ichki yonuv dvigatelli avtomobillarning ekologik ko'rsatkichlari hamda ularning atrof-muhitga ta'sirini baholash.....	87
13	<i>Ko'chimova Dilnoza Ibragim qizi.</i> Kafolat davrida avtomobil ehtiyot qismlarini hisoblash usullarini takomillashtirish orqali avtoservis faoliyati samaradorligini oshirish.....	96
14	<i>Исмаилов Джуманиез Файзуллаевич, Мизрабов Улугбек Боликулович.</i> Влияние технологических параметров процесса высоко температурного диффузионного осаждения на свойства металлов с диффузионными покрытиями.....	102
15	<i>Abdunazarov Jamshid Nurmuxamatovich, Karimova Kamola G'ulomovna, Raxmatov O'tkir Farhod o'g'li.</i> Tormoz ustquymalari ishlab chiqarishda qo'llaniladigan materiallarning kimyoviy tarkibi tahlili.....	107
AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARI VA KOMPYUTER GRAFIKASI		
16	<i>Кузиев Ботир Намозович, Муртазин Эмиль Рустамович.</i> Кибербезопасность в 2024 году: тренды и вызовы.....	114
17	<i>Ostanaqulov Xojiakbar Mansurqul o'g'li.</i> Javascript va reactjs asosida yaratilgan dinamik veb-sahifalarda seo ko'rsatkichlarini oshirish usullarini tadqiq qilish.....	124
ENERGETIKA VA ELEKTROTEXNIKA		
18	<i>Kamoliddin Kadirov Botir Kholdarov, Abdurauf Akhmedov.</i> Step-by-step calculation of energy consumption changes in technological processes of light industry enterprises.....	138
19	<i>Qushakov Sherzod Dilmurod o'g'li.</i> Yarim shaffof quyosh panelari texnologiyalari bo'yicha tadqiqot natijalarini taxlil qilish: yarim shaffof quyosh panellarining yutuq va	145

	kamchiliklari.....	
20	<i>Anarboyev Muhiddin Almonovich, Sattarov Azim Saidovich, Eshqulov Muhriddin Urozboy o'g'li.</i> Energiya resurslarini iqtisod qilishni ilmiy asosda o'rganish natijalari... TO'QIMACHILIK VA YENGIL SANOAT MATERIALLARI TEXNOLOGIYASI	156
21	<i>Doniyorov Bektosh Baxodirovich, Doniyorova Matluba Adashbayevna Shumkarova Shamsiya Pulatovna.</i> Aralash tarkibli ko'ylak-kostyumbop to'qimalarni mustahkamligi bo'yicha loyihalash.....	161
22	<i>Shodmanov Jasur Abdumhammadovich.</i> PVA/GELLAN asosida ikki tarmoqli gel-polimer elektrolitlarning strukturaviy va fizik-kimyoviy tahlili.....	168
23	<i>Kozimjon Sotvoldiyev, Xusanxon Bobojanov, Jahongir Soloxiddinov.</i> Effects of sheath fibers on core-spun yarn quality.....	176
24	<i>Gulruh Matchanova, Jahongir Soloxiddinov, Sherzod Qorabayev, Xusanxon Bobojanov, Suxrob Axmadjanov.</i> Tarash piltasi notekisligini baholash.....	182
25	<i>Yodgorova Hilola Isroilovna.</i> The use of computer graphics in teaching sewing disciplines in the light industry.....	188
26	<i>Matchonova Nargiz Nortayevna.</i> Mahalliy bazalt tolasini fizik-kimyoviy modifikatsiya qilish texnologiyasining ratsional me'yorlarini ishlab chiqish.....	194
27	<i>Махаммадиева Хилола Норбек кизи.</i> Сложный эфир, полученный на основе сивушного масла и сырых жирных кислот хлопкового соапстока – в качестве жирующего агента.....	200
28	<i>Ulug'muradov Xamroz Yusuf o'g'li, Ungarov Jahongirbek Yo'ldosh o'g'li, Yo'ldoshev Xurshid Hazratqulovich, Muradov Rustam Muradovich.</i> Mayda iflosliklardan tozalaydigan laboratoriya uskunasiga turli xil qoziqchalar o'rnatib tajribalar o'tkazish.....	209
29	<i>Ismailov Hamrali Qambarovich, Turg'unov Dilmurod Umarali o'g'li, Babayeva Malikaxon Nabijon qizi.</i> Ventilyator quvurchasi diametri o'zgarishining uning parametrlariga ta'siri.....	215
30	<i>Babayeva Malikaxon Nabijon qizi.</i> Durability test of working parts of harvesting equipment.....	223
31	<i>Musirov Shuxrat Zivaddinovich, Mirzaumidov Asilbek Shuxratjonovich, Turdiev Baxtiyor Ergashovich.</i> Tebranuvchi sirt yuzasidagi chigitlar harakatini nazariy tahlili.. <i>Qorabayev Sherzod Ahmadjonovich, Axmadjonov Suxrob Baxtiyor o'g'li, Adashev</i>	229
32	<i>Boburshox Malikjon o'g'li.</i> Piltaning strukturaviy tuzilishi va tozaligi ip sifatiga ta'sirini baholash.....	234
QURULISH		
33	<i>Akramov Xusnitdin Axrarovich, Raximov Shavkat Turdimurotovich, Mustafaqulov Javohir Rakhmonkul ugli.</i> Composition and structure formation of fine-graded concretes made from raw materials of our republic.....	240
34	<i>Muminov Axat Uktam o'g'li.</i> Yo'l qurilish materiallar xususiyatlarining biki bo'lmagan turdagi qoplamalarni ta'mirlash texnologiyasini tanlashga ta'siri	247
35	<i>Obloqul Berdiyev, G'iyos Narziqulov.</i> Issiqlik himoyalovchi vermikulitli blokning fizik-mexanik xossalarini tadqiq qilish.....	251
36	<i>Raxmatova Gulhayo Erkin qizi.</i> Respublikamizda va horijiy davatlarda ko'p qavatli saqlash joylari va ularning tahlili	255
37	<i>Kamol Abdusamatov.</i> Sanoat chiqindisidan to'ldiruvchi sifatida foydalanib tayyorlangan gazobeton namunalari termofizik xossalarini aniqlash.....	263
38	<i>Sabirov Baxtiyor, Tursunov Bekzod, Mo'minov Axat.</i> Vermikulit, vermikulitning kimyoviy-mineralogik tarkibi, xossalari hamda ularni tadqiq etish usullari.....	268
39	<i>Usmanxodjayeva Lola Asadovna, Utegenova Mahliya Axmad qizi, Xasanova Dilshoda Saydiganixodja qizi.</i> "KO'K GUMBAZ" masjidi binosi zilzilabardoshlilikini sonli tahlil qilish.....	273
40	<i>Ergashov Jasurbek Dilmurodovich.</i> Mahalliy xom ashyo materiallari asosida	281

bazaltfibrobeton texnologiyasi va mustaxkamligining o'ziga xosligi.....

QISQA XABARLAR

- 41 *Pozilov Mamajon Narzikulovich, Karimova Feruza Sattarovna, Sulaymonova Lola Zohid qizi.* Nurota tog' va tog' oldi hududida suv resurslarini ifloslanish xususiyatlari.. 286
- 42 *Mamatov Farmon Murtozayevich, Saparov Shuxratjon Shavkatovich, Turdiev Abdurasul Halilovich, Abdullaev Jo'ra Xudoyorovich, Abdihamidov Nurbek Ural o'g'li.* O'simlik qoldiq poyalarini maydalab tuproq yuzasiga ishlov beruvchi frezaning takomillashgan pichoqlarini o'rganish..... 293
- 43 *Qurbanova Latofat Mamadiyorovna.* Po'lat korroziyasida natriy-karboksimetilselluloza va fosforli birikmalar asosidagi ingibitorlarning samaradorligi..... 300
- 44 *Позилов Мамажон Нарзикулович., Каримова Сидора Бахтиёровна. Жабборова Феруза Исмоиловна, Маликова Мухлиса Акрам кизи. Улашова Амина Эшмурод кизи.* Оценка последствий воздействия айдаркуль-тузкан-арнасайского техногенного объекта на гидрогеологические условия..... 306
- 45 *Tursunov Ahrorbek Aminjon o'g'li, Sharibaev Nosir Yusupjonovich, Tokhirjonova Muattar Rasuljon qizi.* Paxta tozalash korxonalarida ekologik xavfsizlikni ta'minlashda uch bosqichli multi-siklon changsizlantirish tizimining ilmiy asoslari va samaradorlik tahlili..... 314
- 46 *Ahror Tursunov, Sherzod Djurayev, Nosir Sharibaev.* Aqlli filtrlar va gis platformasi asosida paxtasanoatdagi ekologik monitoringni avtomatlashtirish: texnologik yechimlar va tizim modeli..... 321
- 47 *Pozilov Mamajon, Djamolov O'tkir.,* Dual ta'lim – ta'lim sifatini oshirishning samarali usuli..... 329

UDK. 656.05**ANALYSIS OF REDUCING THE IMPACT OF PEDESTRIAN TRAFFIC ON TRAFFIC FLOW IN THE ROAD NETWORK****Baratov Ilhomjon Iskandar o'g'li**

PhD student

Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute

ORCID: 0009-0006-7782-6910

E-mail: ilhom1997phd@gmail.com**Bakirov Lutfilla Yuldashaliyevich**

Doctor of Philosophy in Technical Sciences, Professor

Andijan Institute of Economics and Construction

ORCID: 0009-0007-8471-2089

E-mail: aiqi@edu.uz**Mamayev G'ulom Ibrohimovich**

Doctor of Philosophy in Technical Sciences, PhD

Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute

ORCID: 0000-0001-8407-758X

E-mail: gulom.m1984@gmail.com**Nishonov Azizbek Orziqul o'g'li**

PhD student

Tashkent State University of transport

ORCID: 0009-0001-3739-5101

E-mail: nishonov_azizbek@list.ru**Yusupov Ulug'bek Akmal o'g'li**

2nd year master's student

Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute

E-mail: yusupovulugbek45@gmail.com

Mazkur maqolada shahar yo'l tarmog'ida piyodalar harakati va transport tirbandliklarining transport oqimiga ta'siri o'rganilgan. Tadqiqot davomida piyodalar va transport vositalari o'rtasidagi o'zaro ta'sir mikrodarajada tahlil qilinib, buning uchun Indor Traffic Plan va PTV Vissim kabi modellashtirish dasturlaridan foydalanilgan. Ushbu tadqiqotda shahar transport infratuzilmasida piyodalar zichligi yuqori bo'lgan nuqtalar aniqlanib, u yerda yuzaga keladigan muammolarni bartaraf etish uchun muhandislik yechimlari ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Piyodalar o'tish joyi, transport oqimi, kesishma, harakat oqimi, transport boshqaruvi tizimlari, transport modellari, transport rejalashtirish, Indor Traffic Plan, PTV Vissim.

Настоящая статья посвящена исследованию влияния пешеходного движения и транспортных заторов на поток транспорта в улично-дорожной сети города. Во время исследования взаимодействие между пешеходами и транспортными средствами анализировалось на микроскопическом уровне с использованием программ моделирования, таких как Indor Traffic Plan и PTV Vissim. В ходе работы были выявлены точки насыщения пешеходного движения в городской транспортной

инфраструктуре, а также рассмотрены инженерные решения для устранения возникающих проблем.

Ключевые слова: пешеходный переход, транспортный поток, перекрёсток, управление движением, транспортные модели, транспортное планирование, Indor Traffic Plan, PTV Vissim.

The current article investigates the influence of pedestrian traffic and traffic congestion on the flow of traffic in the urban road network. The interaction between pedestrians and vehicles was analyzed at a microscopic level during the investigation using modeling programs such as Indor traffic plan and PTV Vissim. This study identified pedestrian saturation points in urban transportation infrastructure and looked into engineering solutions to solve the challenges that develop there.

Keywords: Pedestrian crossing, traffic flow, intersection, traffic flow, traffic management systems, traffic models, traffic planning, Indor traffic plan, PTV Vissim.

Introduction

In today's urban road network, effective vehicle and pedestrian traffic management is essential for excellent traffic flow management. The efficiency of traffic flow can be increased by balancing the interactions between cars and pedestrians.

Artificial intelligence-based smart traffic signal systems enable real-time pedestrian and vehicular traffic control. To enhance traffic flow, these devices track pedestrian and vehicle activity and modify signal timing accordingly.

Identifying and eliminating pedestrian-related bottlenecks in urban infrastructure is essential. For example, the type and location of medians have been shown to have a significant impact on pedestrian traffic and traffic flow. Hard medians can help improve traffic flow by reducing pedestrian crossings [1].

Effective traffic flow management in urban centers requires not only vehicle traffic but also pedestrian traffic. By balancing the interaction

between pedestrians and vehicles, overall transportation efficiency can be improved [2].

Main part

For a standardized evaluation of the traffic flow within an urban road network, two elements are mandatory. Firstly, performance measures have to be determined, which are clear measures of traffic operations. Secondly, one has to define different levels of service (LOS), which on one hand characterize the actual traffic flow, and, on the other hand, define a standard for the “desired” traffic flow. For example, the best LOS should represent absolute free flow conditions, where every vehicle is able to travel without any influence by other vehicles, whereas the worst LOS should represent absolute congestion [3]. As of 2022, there are 5 controlled junctions and 6 pedestrian crossings between the intersections of Sh. Rashidov shoh - Baynalminalchilar - Sh. Rashidov shoh- Shifokorlar in Jizzakh. Traffic light cycles govern traffic flow by compelling vehicles to stop at each crossing (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. The research area is based on the situation of 2022

According to the findings of a research done using the Geo tracker and Indor traffic plan applications, the average speed of vehicles driving 1.4 km on Sh. Rashidov shoh was 19.29 km/h, with a maximum speed of 44 km/h, and it took 04:22 minutes to complete the journey. Given that the statistical data was collected

on weekdays and weekends, there are a lot of flaws in terms of traffic problems, such as traffic jams, lost time, and a decrease in average speed when traveling. When examining the traffic flow graph, the average speed was low, owing to many red lights and pedestrian crossings (Figure 2).

Fig. 2. Previous state. Vehicle movement graph

According to the graph above, we can see that as vehicles approach each traffic light and pedestrian crossing, their speed decreases, then accelerates again until they reach the next traffic light, and a certain amount of time is lost along with the speed until they reach a higher speed.

To avoid problems with traffic flow management, the traffic volume of the research item was initially investigated. Surveillance cameras were set at intersections to count the number of vehicles, and video records were taken

during peak hours of the day when there were the most vehicles [4].

Cartograms of junctions were generated using the original data. According to them, the number of vehicles traveling through the Sh.Rashidov shoh - Baynalminalchilar and Sh.Rashidov shoh - Shifokorlar intersections, which mark the beginning and conclusion of Sh.Rashidov shoh in the research object, was 2125 and 1833, respectively. In addition, while constructing the cartogram, analytical data in the form of tables were acquired based on the sorts of vehicles that moved through

the area. According to the results of the study, several traffic problems were observed during the traffic flow management process during peak times of the day, between 08:00-10:00, 12:00-14:00, and 17:00-19:00.

In order to find optimal solutions to existing transport problems, a model of the selected area was created and simulated in the PTV Vissim software package (Figure 3). The transport problems at each intersection were studied through the — Node results section of the program.

Fig. 3. Previous state. Model created in PTV Vissim software

During research at this facility, engineering solutions were established to ensure that existing traffic signal cycles at crossings function properly and to prevent traffic problems by establishing appropriate speeds for cars entering this area. The Sh. Rashidov shoh -

Baynalminalchilar and Sh. Rashidov shoh - Shifokorlar intersections, the construction of 2 underground pedestrian crossings, the reduction of pedestrian crossings by 4, the removal of the green zone separating the road, and the increase in the road strip by 1 (Figure 4).

Fig. 4. After solution engineering. The research area is based on the situation of 2025

As a result, the existing 145-meter traffic jam was reduced by 52 meters, average speed increased to 28.72 km/h,

maximum speed increased to 59 km/h, and travel time fell from 04:22 minutes to 02:49 minutes (Figure 5).

Fig. 5. After solution engineering. Vehicle movement schedule.

Inconclusion

This study looked into the optimization of traffic flow efficiency in metropolitan areas by managing pedestrian traffic and addressing pedestrian congestion in Jizzakh. The study used microscopic modeling tools such as PTV Vissim and Indor Traffic Plan to simulate pedestrian-vehicle interactions in traffic congestion. The primary findings of the study are as follows:

Crosswalks significantly reduced vehicle speeds and caused delays, especially in congested areas in the city center. These obstacles were accurately mapped using the Indor traffic plan, GIS techniques, and real-time traffic monitoring.

According to microscopic simulation modeling, installing underpasses and synchronizing signal control significantly increased the average vehicle speed from

19.29 km/h to 28.72 km/h, the top speed from 44 km/h to 59 km/h, and reduced the

average travel time from 4 minutes 22 seconds to 2 minutes 49 seconds.

Table 1
LOS and performance measures for the evaluation of urban streets and signalized intersections

Indicator	Before then	Before after	Change
Average speed (km/h)	19.29 (km/h)	28.72 (km/h)	+9.43 (km/h) (+48.9%)
Maximum (top) speed ((km/h))	44 (km/h)	59 (km/h)	+15 (km/h) (+34.1%)
Average travel time	4 minutes 22 seconds	2 minutes 49 seconds	-1 minute 33 seconds (-35.4%)
LOS	F	D	F<D

By optimizing simulation-based engineering solutions and pedestrian traffic, this work offers a useful tool for improving urban traffic flow. It highlights the benefits of combining data-driven modeling with smart infrastructure solutions in a mid-sized metropolitan setting.

By optimizing simulation-based engineering solutions and pedestrian traffic, this work offers a useful tool for improving urban traffic flow. It highlights the benefits of combining data-driven modeling with smart infrastructure solutions in a mid-sized metropolitan setting.

Literatures:

1. Fattah, M. A., Morshed, S. R., Morshed, S. Y., Hoque, M. M., & Haque, M. N. (2021). The impact of urban street median in pedestrian behavior and traffic

flow: Experience from a growing city Khulna, Bangladesh. *Transportation Engineering*, 6, 100090.

2. Thakur, S., & Biswas, S. (2019). Assessment of pedestrian-vehicle interaction on urban roads: a critical review. *Archives of transport*, 51.

3. Axer, S., Rohde, J., & Friedrich, B. (2012). Level of service estimation at traffic signals based on innovative traffic data services and collection techniques. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 54, 159-168.

4. Zhankaziev S., Gavriyuk M., Morozov D., Zabudsky A. Scientific and methodological approaches to the development of a feasibility study for intelligent transportation systems/ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/>. Thirteenth International Conference on Organization and Traffic Safety Management in Large Cities (SPbOTSIC 2018).